

Eigenspectral features of some radialene-related π -conjugated systems

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Abstract : π -MO energies of some radialenes (R_n) and radialene-derived quinonoids (R_n^Q) at the Hückel level have been determined graph theoretically. Strong subspectrality is shown to exist among the graph eigenspectra (i.e. the set of HMO energy eigenvalues) and the origin of such subspectrality has been shown to be rooted in rotational symmetry which results in circulant nature of the adjacency matrices of the graphs. The eigenvalues of radialene occur in reciprocal pairs. It was further observed that the HOMO-LUMO gap consistently decreases when each $-\text{CH}_2$ of a radialene is substituted by a quinonoid ring.

Keywords : Radialene, graph theory, circulant matrix, rotational symmetry, eigenvalue.

Introduction

$[n]$ Radialenes (or, $[n]$ methylenecycloalkanes) are conjugated hydrocarbons containing n -membered rings of sp^2 -hybridized C-atoms, to each of which a $=\text{CH}_2$ group is attached. Interest in such systems began long ago¹ after the synthesis of [4]radialene. Hexamethylenecyclohexane, i.e. [6]radialene was synthesized subsequently². Such systems are interesting because of the fact that they are cross-conjugated systems^{3,4}. Graphs representing such systems were shown to have eigenspectra with reciprocal pairs of eigenvalues^{5,6}. Importance of radialenes (and dendralenes) in the design of conducting and ferromagnetic polymers was shown graph theoretically by Dias⁷. The objective of the present note is to show graph theoretically some regular patterns in the π -MO energies of the series of radialenes and radialene-related π -conjugated systems and also to explore the origin of subspectrality in their graph-eigenvalues.

Discussions

A graph G is known⁸ to represent a conjugated π -system with vertices denoting carbon atoms and edges denoting atom connectivities (through sigma bonds). Relationships between graph theory and Hückel Molecular Orbital (HMO) theory are well established⁸⁻¹⁰ and it is known that the eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix of a graph are the same as the π -MO energies of the conju-

gated system which the graph represents (with the Coulomb integral α as the zero and resonance integral β as the unit of energy)⁸⁻¹⁰.

A graph is said to be subspectral to a larger graph if the eigenspectrum of the former is entirely contained in that of the latter. Graphs of radialene-derived systems have rotational symmetry as they always contain a cycle (C_n). Adjacency matrices of such graphs can be block-factored by a procedure given by Davidson and Shen^{11,12} and each block corresponds to the adjacency matrix of a reduced graph. The procedure when applied to the present case, can be briefly summarized as follows :

Let there be a collection of n identical graphs (G) and a cycle, C_n ; the i -th vertex of each G is connected by an edge to one vertex of C_n . The resulting graph is a radialene-derived graph (Fig. 1). Important features of each such graph originate from the fact that adjacency matrices of such graphs can be circulantly partitioned by following a vertex labeling scheme (Davidson-Shen) as explained below.

If there are a total of N vertices in the whole graph, then $N/n = r$ is an integer. If a vertex of C_n is labeled as 1, the other vertices of C_n are labeled as $1 + r, 1 + 2r, \dots, 1 + (n-1)r$. This comprises an orbit. The i -th vertex of G , which is connected to vertex 1, is labeled as 2. Considering rotational symmetry, the similar vertices of the G 's are labeled as $2 + r, 2 + 2r, \dots, 2 + (n-1)r$,

Each diagonal block is the adjacency matrix of a graph with N/n vertices; the block diagonal matrix $A^{(d)}$ is isospectral with the original matrix A .

The block factors correspond to a graph (to be henceforth called the ‘reduced graph’) as shown in Fig. 3, where the vertex weight h is any of the n -th roots of unity, i.e.

$$h = 1, \omega, \omega^2, \dots, \omega^{n-1} \quad (4)$$

Using the reduced graph it now becomes easy to obtain the eigenvalues of the whole graph. The eigenspectra of the smaller graphs, whose adjacency matrices are $A_1, A_2, A_3 \dots A_n$, together constitute the eigenspectrum of the original graph.

Fig. 3. Reduced graph for the general graph shown in Fig.1.

Illustrations

Case 1. Radialenes :

A radialene corresponding to a cycle C_n will be denoted by R_n . In Fig. 4 two such radialenes have been shown. The reduced graph in each case has the same form, namely, an edge with two vertices, of which one

Fig. 4. Graphs for [3]- and [4]radialene and their reduced graphs.

carries a weight h . For [3]radialene the values of h are the cube roots of unity and for [4]radialene the values of h are the fourth roots of unity. Eigenvalues of some radialenes calculated in this way are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Radialene eigenvalues. Number in parenthesis indicates degeneracy of the eigenvalues

Radialene	Eigenvalues
R_3	2.414213, -0.8284271, 0.6180339(2), -1.618034(2)
R_4	$\pm 2.414213, \pm 0.8284271, \pm 1(2)$
R_5	2.414213, -0.8284271, 1.355672(2), 0.477266(2), -0.737642(2), -2.095266(2)
R_6	$\pm 2.414213, \pm 0.8284271, \pm 1.618034(2), \pm 0.6180339(2)$
R_8	$\pm 2.414213, \pm 0.8284271, \pm 1(2), \pm 3.707081(2), \pm 2.292881(2)$

Case II : Radialene-derived π -systems :

If each CH_2 group of a radialene is replaced by a quinonoid ring (with O replaced CH_2), we get a chemically interesting system. Their graphs are radialene-derived graphs, which are amenable to the present graph reduction scheme. Such π -systems will be denoted by R_n^Q to mean that they are derived from R_n on substitution by a quinonoid ring. The reduced graph has a common general form, with values of h depending on n of the cycle C_n in the corresponding radialene. A typical system is shown in Fig. 5 graphs eigenvalues of some radialene-derived graphs determined by the present method are given in Table 2 .

Eigenspectral features of the systems under study

(i) *Subspectrality* : A graph G_1 is subspectral to a larger graph G_2 if all eigenvalues of G_1 are also eigenval-

Table 2. Eigenvalues of some radialene-derived graphs. Number in parenthesis indicates degeneracy of the eigenvalues

Graph	Eigenvalues
R_3^Q	$\pm 1(3), 1, 1.9432006, 2.6137709, -0.068068, -1.356303, -2.1326005, 0.1214328(2), 1.396163962(2), 2.1445279(2), -0.7244327(2), -1.6864739(2), -2.251218(2)$
R_4^Q	$\pm 1(5), \pm 1.9432006, \pm 2.6137709, \pm 0.068068, \pm 1.356303, \pm 2.1326005, \pm 0.3111078(2), \pm 1.4811943(2), \pm 2.1700866(2)$
R_6^Q	$\pm 1(7), \pm 1.9432006, \pm 2.6137709, \pm 0.068068, \pm 1.356303, \pm 2.1326005, \pm 0.1214328(2), \pm 1.396163962(2), \pm 2.1445279(2), \pm 0.7244327(2), \pm 1.6864739(2), \pm 2.251218(2)$

Fig. 5. The molecule R_3^Q , its graph and reduced graph.

ues of G_2 . Table 1 indicates that the eigenvalues of R_3 are all included in the eigenspectrum of R_6 . Similarly, R_4 is subspectral to R_8 , R_5 to R_{10} and so on. In the same way, R_3^Q and R_4^Q are subspectral respectively to R_6^Q and R_8^Q . Reason for such subspectrality lies in the fact that in the radialene series of graphs the reduced graph has a common form, and that the n -th roots of unity are all included in the set of $2n$ -th roots of unity. For example, $(1)^{1/2} = \pm 1$ and $(1)^{1/4} = \pm 1, \pm i$. The same is the reason for the subspectrality of R_3^Q to R_6^Q and R_4^Q to R_8^Q .

(ii) *Validity of the pairing theorem* : For even values of n , all the R_n and R_n^Q graphs are alternant. Hence according to Coulson's pairing theorem¹³, eigenvalues of these graphs occur in \pm pairs. This fact, together with the above subspectrality pattern, makes the task of finding the full eigenspectrum of R_{2n} and R_{2n}^Q from those of R_n and R_n^Q easy. Table 2 shows that the eigenvalues of R_n (and R_n^Q) together with their oppositely signed partners constitute the eigenspectrum of R_{2n} (and R_{2n}^Q).

(iii) *Reciprocity of eigenvalues* : For all radialenes,

the eigenvalues occur in reciprocal pairs $(\lambda, 1/\lambda)$. Hence finding half of the eigenspectrum suffices to get the whole of it. Moreover, radialenes with even-sized rings are alternant systems. Their eigenvalues, therefore occur in reciprocal quartets $(\pm\lambda, \pm 1/\lambda)$. In this case determination of only one-fourth of the eigenspectrum gives the whole of it.

(iv) *HOMO-LUMO gap* : The eigenvalues given in the Tables 1 and 2 show that the HOMO-LUMO gap consistently decreases when each $-\text{CH}_2$ of a radialene is substituted by a quinonoid ring (i.e. in converting R_n to R_n^Q). This was observed for R_3^Q , R_4^Q and R_6^Q .

Conclusion

Subspectrality in the HMO eigenvalues of the series radialenes and radialene-related quinonoids is due to the circulant nature of the adjacency matrices of the molecular graphs resulting from rotational symmetry. This, together with reciprocity of the eigenvalues and the pairing theorem, greatly reduces the task of determination of the full eigenspectra of large radialene-derived systems.

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